

DETECTION OF EATING BEHAVIOR DISORDERS IN STUDENTS BEFORE THE EXAM USING THE DEBQ QUESTIONNAIRE

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Annotation: The combination of emotional, external and restrained types of eating behaviour was present in 26% of patients, of which 90% are women. Risk factors of eating disorders were identified: female gender, diabetes and arterial hypertension in patient s relatives, long histories of type 2 diabetes and arterial hypertension in a patient, high levels of personal anxiety and depression.

Keywords: DEBQ, external eating behaviour, emotional eating behavior, before the exams

Relevance. It is known that passing the exam is sometimes exciting, sometimes fearful and anxious for every student. Of course, these emotional states affect not only the mental state of the body, but also the eating behavior. The tendency to obesity in the body and disorders of gastrointestinal functions are also largely related to eating behavior. in today's modern medicine, the close relationship between psychosomatics, that is, the psyche and the health of the body, is studied in many scientific studies. In particular, the relationship between eating behavior and various metabolic diseases in the body has been studied a lot, and most of the research results indicate that the health of the body is closely related to eating behavior. for example: To estimate the eating behaviour disorders in overweight and obese patients 73 patients from 27 up to 70 years were examined. With the help of the DEBQ 87,6% of patients were identified eating behaviour disorders. External and restrained types of eating behaviour were revealed more often. The combination of emotional, external and restrained types of eating behaviour was present in 26% of patients, of which 90% are women. Risk factors of eating disorders were identified: female gender, diabetes and arterial hypertension in patient s relatives, long histories of type 2 diabetes and arterial hypertension in a patient, high levels of personal anxiety and depression. In some cases, we face stressful situations that last for several weeks. Naturally, in such situations, eating behavior disorders are observed, which increases the risk of developing somatic diseases in the body.

The purpose of scientific research. detection of eating behavior disorders in students before the exam using the DEBQ questionnaire

Material and method. In the study, we used the DEBQ questionnaire and the Kettle index to determine overweight. the study was conducted on 50 2nd and 3rd year students who were about to take the winter session exams.

Research results. 63 students were initially divided into groups based on gender differences. 35 (56%) of the students who passed the exam are girls, 28 (44%) are boys.

All students were given the DEBQ questionnaire online via their mobile device. Using this method, firstly, time was saved, and secondly, unnecessary wastage of paper was avoided. after that, each student's body weight and height were measured. To avoid unnecessary discomfort in the medical room of the student residence, we used a scale and a height meter. The results of the DEBQ survey were as follows: 11 of the girls examined had restrictive eating, 10 had emotional eating, and 7 had externalizing eating behaviors. It was found that 13 of the examined boys had restrictive eating behavior, 10 had emotional eating behavior, and 12 had external eating behavior.

Weight, mass, and height of all subjects were measured and entered into the Kettle index formula, they were found to be above the norm, with 29% having restrictive eating behaviors, 35% emotional eating behaviors, and 36% binge eating. 12% of those with emotional eating behaviors were found to be overweight and obese.

Conclusions. According to the results of the study, emotional type predominated in girls, and restrictive eating behavior type predominated in boys. It is concluded that before the exams, boys have more digestive disorders and susceptibility to illness.

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